

LITRARY APPROACHES OF NARRATIVE FEATURE IN “ VANITY FAIR”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037138>

Annotation. This article provides that literary approaches to novel “ Vanity Fair” and describes the features of Narrative character in it.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada “Manmanlik yarmarkasi” romanida adabiy yondashuvlar hamda hikoya janrining xususiyatlari yoritib berilgan.

Key words: analyze, feature, character, story, literary, text

Vanity Fair tells the story of a young woman's rise and fall from the shallow top of England's upper class. Vanity Fair also focuses on the people who inhabit this world, including Becky's friend Amelia Sedley, who in many ways lives parallel to Becky. The story itself is presented as part of a puppet show that the narrator introduces at the beginning of the novel. The main conflict revolves around Becky Sharp, the orphaned daughter of an artist and dancer, and her ambitions for higher social status and money. Becky grew up socializing with members of the middle and upper classes in the schools these students attended and where Becky worked in exchange for some lessons. These early contacts made her acutely aware of the great gulf between her and the upper echelons of British society.

I analyzed a passage in the 44th chapter of Vanity Fair. This was little Raw-don, a boy with a very open face, always tenderly attached to all those who were good to him, but not to his mother. One day, he wanted to hear his mother, Rebecca, sing, but when she noticed him, she hit him several times in the ear; he ran to his kitchen friends, the servants, for comfort. Lord Steyne, Rebecca's lover, also dislikes Rawdon and the young man considers him an enemy. The Kitchen Inquisition judges Rebecca and knows everything about her. The secret trial of the servants' hall decides whether she is guilty or not.

This text presents narration as well as direct and indirect descriptions. The narrative is presented with sentences such as “The cook looked at the maid, the maid deliberately looked at the servant”, “After this incident, the mother's dislike turned into hatred”, “And there was a time when A short time later, [...] the doorman opened the door, the uniformed servants in the hallway, the civil servants in white vests, [...], all knew her.” Direct description is the process of revealing a character's personality through the use of adjectives, expressions or descriptive adjectives such as "good", "open-faced", "generous-hearted and gentle"... Indirect description is the process of revealing a character's

personality through the character's words (e.g., "It's not because it hurts me, [...], it's just..."), actions (e.g. : "His mother came out and beat him violently with several blows to the ears."), appearance (e.g. "He has blue eyes and wavy blonde hair"), etc. Additionally, the author deviates from narration throughout the novel, using direct address (e.g., "Madam, your secret will be revealed") and second-person pronouns (e.g. example: "If you are guilty, tremble with fear").

This text can be divided into three parts. The first part ends with the words "He was bored with her" and the second part ends with the words "...the tall man in colorful clothes at his side."

- The first part is full of adjectives when describing the boy's appearance and personality "He was a handsome boy with an open face, blue eyes and wavy flaxen hair, strong limbs but with generous and gentle heart, affectionately attached to all those who were good to him. The enumeration of Raw-don's attachments, expressed in reverse, - "to the horse - to the groom [...] - to Molly, the cook, [...] - to Briggs [...] and especially is with his father [...] » helps create a humorous effect. In addition, there is an indirect description of Rebecca:

"She doesn't like him [the child]. ...He bored her. These sentences reveal Rebecca to be a callous and mean woman who despises and neglects her children. Thackeray tries to arouse sympathy for the boy in the readers and make them feel sorry for him.

- The second part describes the series of events that happened to baby Raw-don. His mother hit him a few times in the ear because he heard her singing. There is another indirect description of Rebecca, demonstrating her savagery and callousness. She deeply insults her son with "this free and innocent display of Becky's character," as the author says, which confirms that she is prone to hitting him. "The boy's heart is bleeding," they said. Placing "it is" or "it was" before a phrase is a common method of emphasis. There is a kitchen inquisition sitting in every house that judges and knows everything, now in charge of Rebecca. In the sentence "The chef looked at the maid; the maid deliberately looked at the servant [...] » parallelism is used. Parallel structures are often accompanied by repetition of one or more words. The uniformity of structure and vocabulary highlights the fact that everyone in the servants' quarters is drawn into gossip. There is also mention of Lord Steyne, Rebecca's lover, who "also did not like the boy at all", as Thackeray puts it. This excerpt is filled with anger, hatred and bitterness, all the characters are on the battlefield.

- The third part is a digression from the text. The first sentence of this section is "My God! How terrible, this servant's interrogation! Thackeray here deviates

from the narrative that represents his views on contemporary society. Here the author comments on the events described, reflects on the evils of the bourgeois world, expresses his philosophical views on life. In this excerpt there is a description of the servant's room, and Thackeray uses metonymy, the transfer of the name of one object to another to which it is somehow related, in the sentence "Discover a way respectfully walked towards her. [...] – with Slander [...] behind him [...]". The abstract nouns "discover" and "slander" are used instead of the names of people who are the living embodiment of these evils, who slandered (slandered), finding out the details of their lives. other people's lives. Digression from the text is also expressed through the use of direct address and second person pronouns, drawing the reader into the events of the book and giving greater generalization to the book. paragraph. It is used in the sentences "Madam, your secret will be revealed [...]" and "If you are guilty, tremble in fear." [...] If you are not guilty, have a care of appearances [...]".

In the novel "Vanity Fair", as in any classical literary work "linear visuality and the density of the page filling could not be violated. That is why genetically existent necessity of combination of the verbal and iconic was expressed in pictures on the margins of the manuscript and illustrations [5, p. 227]. It is worth mentioning that in the 19th century the illustrations of the English attained their bloom. Thus, the drawings of the poet and artist W. Blake, which mostly depict mythical creatures and biblical characters, are symbolic. This is quite consistent with the romanticism in the context of which W. Blake created. We see the symbolism and metaphor in the illustrations of V. M. Thackeray. In an allegorical, metaphorical game with the reader, the writer creates a mixture of fiction and reality, which is a consequence of the influence of the romantic tradition, with which he seems to argue.

At the same time in the first half of the 19th century. illustrators mostly imitated allusive and allegorical drawings by Hogarth and caricatures by J. Gillray and T. Rowlandson and created "talking" drawings [3, p. 60]. Illustrations to the novels of W. Thackeray's contemporary, Charles Dickens, belong to this type. As for the novel "Fair of Vanity", the fact that the author and illustrator is one person who expresses his own thoughts verbally and visually is extremely important. In view of this, we use the terms "author's drawing" and "illustration" as synonymous. Considering these drawings-illustrations by VM Thackeray, we take into account the work of R. Barthes' "Rhetoric of Image", which deals with the need to study the illustration from a structural point of view and answer the question "Is the image excessive in relation to the text or it duplicates the

information contained in the text, or vice versa, the text contains additional information that is missing in the image2, p. 302].The narrative discourse of the novel “Fair of Vanity” is complemented by drawings, which V. M. Thackeray filled his work. Since in modern editions of the novel “Vanity Fair” the author’s drawings are virtually absent, we can talk about the pre-dominance of the verbal component and the accompanying role of illustrations. Indeed, in the first editions the spatial arrangement of verbal and iconic elements is due to communicative, aesthetic and semantic tasks [4, p. 190]. Yes, the first letters of the sections are designed as pictures.

Almost every section has illustrations for the entire page with the caption, as well as one or more drawings of different sizes. Thus, there is an external correlation between the verbal components and the drawings, ie a deictic connection without close cohesion.

A basic function of the author’s pictures is visual embodiment of the text, that exposes the contents of the book. It refers to the traditions of the Victorian literature.

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